

Application to RT-qPCR virus diagnostic supported in High-Performance Computing

Francisco Martinez-Perez¹ Lina Vera-Cala², Diego Rueda¹ and Carlos Barrios-Hernández¹

¹Large-Scale and Advanced Computing Research Group – CAGE. Universidad Industrial de Santander, Bucaramanga, Cl. 9 # Cra 27, Santander, Colombia.

fjmartin@uis.edu.co

²Research group on demography, public health and health systems – GUINDESS; Universidad Industrial de Santander, Bucaramanga, Cl. 9 # Cra 27, Santander, Colombia.

Keywords: High-Performance Computing, Biological Public Database, One-Step RT-qPCR diagnostic, Bioinformatics applications to biomedicine, Influenza A H1N1 and SARS-CoV-2

Abstract. The Polymerase Chain Reaction and Next Generation sequencing has allowed millions of nucleotide sequences are organized with bioinformatics; they are available in public databases which have software designed to understand their regulation and/or constitutive elements among other approaches. Even when these developments allowed establishing thermodynamic conditions for experimental implementations, sometimes the nucleotide or protein sequences have incomplete regions that limit the use of information. Since 2014 developed HPC procedures to eliminate this type of nucleotide sequences to generate data bases and develop tools that allow establish the possible interactions between a molecules designed for the diagnosis of the HINI influenza A virus and SARS-CoV- 2. We show an application that have allowed obtain the putative habitation pattern between primers an amplification region and thereby establish the efficiency of RT-PCR applied to the identification of these viruses.

1. Introduction

In the history of humanity, viruses have generated several pandemics. Among the main ones are those related to the respiratory tract since the viruses use them to generate their dispersion and therefore the contagion rate is higher compared to those that require blood tracts to carry out their replication. An example of the above are the Influenza virus that generate the flu.

In this sense, on January 30, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) reported public health emergency with the outbreak of the new coronavirus now known as SARS-CoV-2 and in this, he stressed the need to generate diagnostic systems to decrease viral dispersal inviting the scientific community to produce them¹.

However, one of the main problems at that time was that the genomic structure of SARS-CoV-2 was unknown, which was reported on January 24, 2020² and on March 11 the current pandemic was declared³. From the beginning and like other scientific groups, in February 2020 we generated an *in silico* RT-qPCR diagnostic system, but as other proposals, experimental validation was requested for its publication, which was not possible because at that time COVID-19 was present only in some countries⁴.

In Colombia, the first patient identified with SARS-CoV-2 was on March 6, 2019, who was returning from Italy where the pandemic was already beginning to spread⁵. In that same month,

the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation of Colombia (Minciencias) invited national scientific groups to generate proposals that would help reduce the spread and effects of the pandemic in six lines of action⁶. The proposal that was approved was related to the diagnosis by RT-qPCR of SARS-CoV-2 and Influenza A H1N1, which was based on the similarity at the level of their nucleotide composition, genomic aspects, pattern of appearance, dispersion and evolution that were beginning to have the SARS-CoV-2 genomes regarding the Hemagglutinin, Nuclear Protein and Matrix Proteins M1-M2 genes of the Influenza A H1N1 virus that we have studied from the beginning of the 2009 pandemic to the present day⁷.

But the key to the success of the genomic study of both viruses, which allowed the generation of diagnostic systems by RT-PCR and their sequencing with new generation technologies, has been the development of high-performance supercomputing systems that allow the analysis of thousands of genomic sequences that are generated daily in public databases such as GenBank or GISAID.

Previous this work, we developed a bioinformatic applications on the GUANE⁸ supercomputer of the Center for Supercomputing and Scientific Calculation of the Industrial University of Santander (SC3UIS) in Colombia that allow the genomes and nucleotide sequences reported in both databases to be analyzed in minutes or hours and with to carry out molecular, genomic and evolutionary studies but specially to validate the efficiency of the first and probes used in the diagnosis by RT-qPCR. The application downloads and eliminate sequences with indeterminate nucleotides or incomplete regions in an orderly and usable way from a personal computer. The sequences are obtained from GenBank with the NCBI “Entrez Programming Utilities” API; while those published in GISAID or in Influenza Research DataBase (IRDB), the download is manually. For any of the databases, only the range of years, months and search terms is defined. From the selected sequences, the identity and homology patterns of the nucleotide positions are determined by aligning them with the MAFFT software implemented in GUANE with the parameters of the DNA Loss Model, which determines the mutational pattern that generates new genes from of an ancestor gene⁹.

The new application developed obtains the number of possible nucleotide combinations between one or more consensus sequences with respect to the primers and the probe used in the diagnosis by RT-qPCR. The application will produce two types of results: when it is 1 it represents 100% identity between all the sequences of the RT-qPCR which suggests a successful diagnosis, but if it is different than 1, the number corresponds to the possible sequences that will not be amplified and that will generate false negative diagnoses.

2. Results and Discussion

The prototype application allows: 1) Registering the genomic sequences or consensus genes, either monthly or annually, regardless of the virus. 2) Register the different types of primers and probes designed for diagnosis by any variant of PCR or RT-PCR. 3) Relate the primers and probes designed for diagnosis by any PCR or RT-PCR variant with one or more genomes or consensus sequences. It carries out the conceptual translation of the nucleotide sequence of the primers and probes with respect to the first nucleotide of the initial codon and in case of nucleotide variations in the first or second position of the codon, it shows all the possible amino acids from the first complete codon. 4) Locates the nucleotide region with the greatest homology to the primer and/or probe sequence within the related consensus sequences. 4) Places the antisense nucleotide sequence in the sense direction.

2.1 Registration of genomic sequences or consensus genes

For the use of the application, the first step that must be carried out is the registration of a consensus sequence, which requires the information which are register in the boxes indicated in Figure 1:

- (1) The consensus genomic or gene sequence as a text string that can be copied directly from an application such as Bioedit or Jalview that allow this consensus to be generated from a set of aligned sequences as indicated in the first section.
- (2) The start date with which the consensus sequence was generated.
- (3) The final date of the sequences used to obtain this consensus.
- (4) A reference that makes it possible to identify this consensus with respect to the other registered consensuses.

Once the registration of the genomic sequence or the consensus gene has been completed, the prototype application allows the inclusion of more consensus sequences, which are entered through the previous process. When the registration is completed, the application is redirected to the list of genomic sequences or consensus genes, where all registered in the application are presented in order by final date of creation of the consensus sequence and it shows them to the user from the date most recent and lastly the oldest. In addition, the option is given to: view, edit or delete each registered consensus.

A

Register a new Consensus

Consensus* (1)

```
YRTCCGKTTGACBCYKAYATCAQYACATAGKTTTHKYCCGGGTGAYDKMAAGSTRAKATGGAGAGYCTTGCCCTGGTTTCAACGAG
AAAACACACRTCCARCTYAGTTGGCTGTTTTACMGGTYCGYSACGTRYTYRTMCGTGGCTTTGGRGACTCCGTGGAGGAGGTMTTATCAGA
BDCACGTCACATYTTAAAGAYKQYACTTGTGGCTYAGTAGAAGTTGAAAAGDCRTYTTGCTGAACTTGAACAGCCYTAGTSTTYATYAAC
GTTYDGAHGTCCGAACTGCAYCTYAWGGTERTSWTRTGKTTGAKYTGATGACAGARYTCGMAGKGCATTGACAGCTYGTAGTGGTGAGACA
YTTGGTGYCTGTGTCCTYATDTGKGGGAARTACCACTGRCCTTAYGRCAAKRTTCTYTTCCYAGAAACGGTAATAAAGSAGCTGKTGGCCATA
RYTAYGRGCGHATYAAAKTCATTTGMCTTMKCCGRGAGCTTGGCACWAGYCTYAVGAAGATTTCAAGAAAAYTGGAACTAATACATR:
GCAGTGGTGYACCGSTGAAGTCATGGGTAACCTTAACGGRRGGGCATACACTYGYATDTYGATAWAACYCTGTGGCCYTSAYGGGTACY
MTCTTGAGTGCATTAANKACCTTCTAGCAYGTGGTAAAGCTTYATGCAYTTTGTGACAAAYTRGACTTATTREAYYTAARAGGGGTGTA
TAYTCTGCGCHTRGACATGAGCATGAAATTRCTGGTACACGGARCDYCTGAAARGAGCTATGAATGCRARACGCTTTTBAATTAAMTTGS
CAANGAATTTGACAYCTTYAATGRRGAATGTGCAMTTTGTATTGCCCTTAATTCYATATCAAGACTATTCACCAAGCGTTTBAAAKAAA
AKCTTGAAGGCTTATGGGTAAGNTYCGATCTGTATCCAGTGGTCACYYAARTGARTGCAACCAAAATGTGGCTTYAADYCTCATGAAKTGT
```

Start date* (2) End date* (3)

Referenciar* (4)

[Create](#)

B

Consensus List

[Add consensus](#)

Reference	Length	Start Date	End Date	Options
NCBI OCTUBRE 2020	30102	Oct. 1, 2020	Oct. 31, 2020	View Edit Delete
NCBI SEPTIEMBRE 2020	30102	Sept. 1, 2020	Sept. 1, 2020	View Edit Delete
NCBI AGOSTO 2020	30102	Aug. 1, 2020	Aug. 31, 2020	View Edit Delete
NCBI JULIO 2020	30102	July 1, 2020	July 1, 2020	View Edit Delete
NCBI JUNIO 2020	30102	June 1, 2020	June 30, 2020	View Edit Delete
NCBI MAYO 2020	30102	May 1, 2020	May 31, 2020	View Edit Delete
NCBI ABRIL 2020	30102	April 1, 2020	April 1, 2020	View Edit Delete
NCBI MARZO 2020	30102	March 1, 2020	March 1, 2020	View Edit Delete
NCBI FEBRERO 2020	30102	Feb. 1, 2020	Feb. 29, 2020	View Edit Delete
NCBI ENERO 2020	30102	Jan. 1, 2020	Jan. 31, 2020	View Edit Delete

Figure 1. Consensus registration window. The 4 types of data necessary for registration consensus sequence or of the selected gene are indicated in red numbers between parentheses (A). List of registered consensus genes or genomes in order of date. The columns display the record data.

2.2 Registration of Primers and Probes

The execution of this part of the process in relation to the registration of primers and probes for the prototype application will be called indistinctly with the word "Primer" which is preceded by the word that indicates the direction of the primer or the one that generates the light signal. Therefore, a Primer is considered to be composed of three inputs:

- (1a) The nucleotide sequence of the Sense Primer (5'-3') Forward Primer.
- (1b) The nucleotide sequence of the probe that generates the light signal in the sense direction (5'-3'), Quench Primer (optional)
- (1c) The nucleotide sequence of the Primer in the antisense (3'-5') direction Reverse Primer. It is noteworthy that the application generates the direction position (5'-3') automatically.

Additionally, a written reference is requested that allows distinguishing the primer indicated in the entry (2a) and a URL link where the primer is registered. This can be a link to a scientific article or an access key of the nucleotide sequence with which it was designed and is recorded in the entry (2b). Figure. 2A.

In the following entry that is indicated with the number (3) it means that in the prototype application one or more genomic sequences or consensus genes must be selected so that they are related to the Primer that is being registered and with this the Primer-analysis is achieved. Consensus. Figure. 2A.

The prototype application has three advanced options indicated by the number four and the first three letters of the alphabet, namely; 4a, 4b, 4c. In addition, in this section you have the option of placing the position of the first or second nucleotide of the codon at the 5' end of the Forward

A

B

Seq Primer	Qn Primer	Rev Primer	References	Options
ACAGTACCTTAATAGTAAAGCCT	ACACAGCCACCTTACCTGCTCG	ATATTCAGCACTAGCAGCA	Covid Primer E	Edit Delete
ATATAGCTTATGTCATGATGC	GAGGAAGCAATCCCAATTCAGTTTCTTCTAT	TTAAGACATAGCCAGTACCC	Covid Primer LAB	Edit Delete

Figure 2. In "A" the Primer registration window is shown, indicating the required entries. The red numbering corresponds to the information that must be placed according to what is indicated in the text. In "B". Example of the list of Primers and Probes registered in the Prototype Application. Note that the last column shows the editing dialog box and the others show the primers and probe corresponding to the "E" and "lab" genes.

Primer and Quench, so that the system can estimate the possible amino acids from the indicated position of the next codon. In the case of the Reverse Primer, the selection of the codon nucleotides corresponds to the last two nucleotides of the antisense direction. Figure. 2A.

Upon completing the Primer registration, the user is redirected to the Primers list where all entries are displayed and the option to view details, edit or delete the listed Primers is given as shown in Figure 2B.

2.3 Relate the primers and probes designed for diagnosis by any PCR or RT-PCR variant with one or more genomes or consensus sequences.

Upon completion of a successful registration of primers and probes, the prototype application initiates an automatic analysis process on these and the relationships with the consensus sequences. Starting from the list of Primers. The user can enter the "View Details" option identified with a magnifying glass to learn more about the analysis performed.

Initially, as shown in Figure 3, number (1) shows 3 tabs: the first for each registered primer and/or probe, together with a section (1a) where the conceptual translation of the nucleotide sequence of primers and probes. In addition, this section indicates the number of nucleotide sequences that can be generated from positions with more than two possible nucleotides. To facilitate visual inspection by the user, each primer is color coded Forward Primer in green, Quench Primer in yellow, and Reverse Primer in red.

Figure 3. Example of the presentation of the results of the Prototype Application with the primers and probes for the diagnosis of Sars Cov.2 by RT-PCR. based on all Gen E used in the diagnosis authorized by the WHO and the INS (A) and Gen S "Spike" which is directly related to the infection to the patient (B). In the upper left part, the result of the advanced option that shows the conceptual translation of the selected Primer. Note the nucleotide sequence detail of the primers and probes that are obtained after searching the gene or genomic consensus sequences. Observe in the boxes of each nucleotide the monthly mutations that will affect the hybridization pattern in the One-Step Real-Time RT-PCR diagnosis. The numbers in the column named RT-PCR indicate the number of combinations and their total in the diagnosis. The red numbers in parentheses correspond to the instructions in the text.

In the lower part (2a, 2b, 2c), a table is generated with all the consensus sequences related to the current primer, applying text processing techniques, the nucleotide region with the greatest homology to the primer sequence is located, so that mutations in the different consensus sequences can be analyzed and the mutations that have occurred at each position are indicated. In (2d) the total number of nucleotide sequence options that will be had as a function of the number of degeneracies of the primers and probe is shown.

Conclusions

Due to their versatility with respect to the global mutational patterns of the new SARS-CoV-2 strains reported in the databases, these tools can contribute to establish the amino acid change of a region used for the generation of antibody epitopes and even determine the nucleotide changes in the regions used for RNA vaccines that are implemented in various countries of the world, among others.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to express their gratitude to High Performance and Scientific Computing Center of the Industrial University of Santander, the Vice-Rector of Research and Extension of the Industrial University of Santander, and Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation with the invitation No. 1015, Mincienciaton. Contract 369-2020.

Funding

This research was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technology, and Innovation of Colombia (Minciencias) [contract No. 369-2020, code 1102101576900] and by the Vice-Rector of Research and Extension of Industrial University of Santander [project No. 76900].

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

References

- 1 World Health Organization. Statement on the second meeting of the International Health Regulations (2005) Emergency Committee regarding the outbreak of novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV). WHO. 2020; : 1–7. [https://www.who.int/news/item/30-01-2020-statement-on-the-second-meeting-of-the-international-health-regulations-\(2005\)-emergency-committee-regarding-the-outbreak-of-novel-coronavirus-\(2019-ncov\)](https://www.who.int/news/item/30-01-2020-statement-on-the-second-meeting-of-the-international-health-regulations-(2005)-emergency-committee-regarding-the-outbreak-of-novel-coronavirus-(2019-ncov)) (accessed Jan 03, 2021).
- 2 Zhu N, Zhang D, Wang W, *et al.* A novel Coronavirus from patients with Pneumonia in China, 2019. *new engl J Med* 2020; **382**: 727–33.
- 3 World Health Organization. WHO Director-General's opening remarks at the media briefing on COVID-19 - 11 March 2020. WHO. 2020; : 1–4. <https://www.who.int/director-general/speeches/detail/who-director-general-s-opening-remarks-at-the-media-briefing-on-covid-19---11-march-2020> (accessed Jan 05, 2021).
- 4 Nozaki I, Miyano S. The necessity of continuous international cooperation for establishing the coronavirus disease 2019 diagnostic capacity despite the challenges of fighting the outbreak in home countries. *Glob Heal Med* 2020; **2**: 145–7.
- 5 Ministerio de Salud y Protección Social. Colombia confirms its first case of COVID-19. Minsalud. 2020; : 1–2. <https://www.minsalud.gov.co/English/Paginas/Colombia-Confirms-Its-First-Case-of-COVID-19.aspx> (accessed Jan 04, 2021).
- 6 Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación. Invitation to present projects that contribute to the solution of current health problems related to the COVID-19 pandemic. Minciencias. 2020; : 1–2. <https://minciencias.gov.co/convocatorias/invitacion-para-presentacion-propuestas/invitacion-presentar-proyectos-que-contribuyan> (accessed Jan 05, 2021).

- 7 Vera-Cala L, Barrios-Hernandez C, Martinez-Perez F. Contribution to the diagnostic protocol of Coronavirus COVID-19 and Influenza A H1N1 Virus by real-time RT-PCR of a step authorized by the World Health Organization with the inclusion of marker genes required for viral infection and their validation by Next-generation genomic sequencing with nucleotide concentration technology. *Minciencias*. 2020; : 1–5. <https://minciencias.gov.co/mincienciaton/proyectos> (accessed Jan 06, 2021).
- 8 Centro de Super Computación y Cálculo Científico UIS. GUANE (GpUs Advanced computiNg Environment). UIS. 2017; : 1–3. http://wiki.sc3.uis.edu.co/index.php/Cluster_Guane (accessed Jan 06, 2021).
- 9 Cadena-Caballero CE, Vera-Cala LM, Barrios-Hernandez C et al. Denaturing and dNTPs reagents improve SARS-CoV-2 detection via single and multiplex RT-qPCR [version 1; peer review: 1 approved with reservations]. *F1000Research* **2022**, 11:331 (<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.109673.1>)